

INTERFACE REACTION AND CHARACTERIZATION

IN B/AL COMPOSITES

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Interfacial reactions, strength degradation and fracture morphology have been characterized in B/Al(1100) and B/Al(6061) composite systems at $V_f = 0.55$. Reaction was promoted by isothermal exposure at 350°C or 500°C for times up to 8.6×10^5 s. Tetragonal AlB_{12} was identified as the reaction product in the 6061 matrix and hexagonal AlB_2 in the 1100 matrix. Interface development is analyzed based on a moving boundary model, modified by the addition of ternary elements. While strength decreases in both systems, the time dependence of elevated temperature exposure is different in the two matrix materials. In the 45° fiber orientation, failure occurs primarily by matrix shear whereas in the 90° fiber orientation, fracture morphology is characterized by a mixture of fiber splitting, ductile matrix fracture and failure at fiber-matrix interfaces.

Introduction

The interface between constituents of a composite provides the means for stress transfer from matrix to reinforcement. Thus, a detailed and quantitative understanding of the structure and stability of the interface is necessary if the full potential of advanced composites is to be achieved. In metal matrix composite systems, interfacial degradation can occur during composite fabrication and on subsequent isothermal exposure (thermal aging) or thermal cycling during elevated temperature service. Typically, a reaction zone develops and this frequently gives rise to a loss in performance as reflected in decreased strength, ductility and toughness. Inhibition or minimization of the reaction zone and maintenance of interface integrity is therefore essential for optimum properties.

It is known that several time-temperature-stress-atmosphere combinations influence the composite interface and structure in B/Al. Pronounced thermal aging has been confirmed with a significant degradation in ambient temperature strength; a combination of cyclic load and thermal aging accelerated the effect (1). Thermal cycling has also been shown to result in a decrease in tensile strength and modulus (2,3). Further, the level of property degradation was strongly influenced by the prevailing atmosphere. White and Wright (4) have observed a much larger decrease in longitudinal and transverse strength in air as compared to argon for B/Al composites cycled up to 6000 times between ambient and 425°C. Surface roughening of the boron and pore formation at the interface were more evident in the air cycled composites (3,4) than in those cycled in argon.

Observations by Grimes et al. (3) indicate that thermal cycling provides a more severe condition re interface stability than isothermal aging at similar temperatures. Tensile property degradation was more rapid in the 1100 matrix system than in the composite having a 6061 alloy matrix. White and Wright (4) examined thermal cycling in the 1100, 2024 and 6061 aluminum alloy-boron systems. Fibers extracted from air-cycled composites had a lower strength than those cycled in argon. The matrix alloy composition also influenced the extent of property degradation; 2024 and 6061 were more susceptible than 1100.

Olsen and Tompkins (5) examined the effects of continuous and cyclic thermal exposures in boron and Borsic[®] - reinforced 6061 matrix systems. It is believed that the compound $(AlMg)B_2$ forms in the interface reaction zone. Composites were exposed at 455°C for up to 8.6×10^5 s and at 510°C for up to 4.3×10^4 s. Isothermal exposure did not affect strength in the Borsic[®]/aluminum. However, thermal cycling did promote strength degradation, particularly in B/Al.

These studies have served to confirm interface instability and associated property degradation in B/Al. In the present work the goal has been to quantitatively identify interface structures as a function of thermal history and to monitor strength level. To this end optical and scanning electron microscopy and x-ray diffraction techniques have been utilized to define: interface morphology and composition; diffusion and growth kinetics of interface reactions; degradation and debonding.

Experimental Procedure

A. Materials, Thermal Treatment and Interface Observations

B/Al composites in the form of sheet panels 1.347mm thick were fabricated at the United Technologies Research Center by an advanced diffusion bonding technique. The aluminum alloy matrix was either 1100 or 6061 reinforced

to a volume fraction (V_f) of 0.55. Filament diameter was 142 μ m and 203 μ m in the 6061 and 1100 matrix materials respectively.

Reaction at the matrix-fiber interface was induced by isothermal exposure of the composite materials at temperatures of 350°C and 500°C for times up to 8.6x10⁵s in air or dry argon. Reaction products resulting from isothermal exposure were observed by first extracting the aluminum alloy matrix from around the boron fibers using a 10% HCl or 10% NaOH solution. Optical and scanning electron microscopy were then used in the examination.

B. X-Ray Diffraction

The Debye-Scherrer x-ray diffraction method was used to identify reaction products formed at the matrix-fiber interface resulting from thermal exposure of the composites. After extracting the matrix, reaction products were observed in the form of fine particles on the surfaces of the boron fibers. It was necessary to separate the particles from the fiber surface in order to avoid superimposition of the diffraction lines from those of the fiber substrate. Separation was achieved by first extracting fibers from the matrix. The fibers were then taped onto a glass slide and a strip of cellulose acetate tape, moistened with acetone, applied to the fiber surfaces. After drying, the fine particles of reaction product adhered to the tape which was then stripped from the fibers. The tape was then cut into narrow strips for loading into quartz capillary tubes prior to exposure by CuK_α radiation (Ni filter). Exposure times up to 86.4x10³s were necessary for adequate diffracted intensity.

C. Tensile Testing

Composite panels 76.2mm long x 6.3mm wide were cut by electric discharge machining. Fiber orientation, with respect to the stress axis, was 90° or 45°; a few specimens were cut at the 0° orientation. All tests were conducted at room temperature in a standard Instron machine at a cross head speed of 4.2 x10⁻⁶ms⁻¹. Adhesively bonded tabs of aluminum were attached to each side of the test panels in the grip area to prevent premature failure due to fiber breakage within the grips.

Results

A. Thermodynamic Stability Calculations

Utilizing the Manlabs-National Physical Laboratory material data bank (6), thermodynamic stability calculations were made for eleven reactions in order to assess relative reaction product stability.

Temperature dependence of the free energies for each reaction is illustrated in Figures 1 through 4. Free energies of formation of the possible compounds which may form during thermal aging in the B/Al system are summarized in Table I. While the data reflect relative stabilities, they provide no insight into growth kinetics.

Growth of the interface reaction products is dependent upon several factors and includes the thermodynamic stability of boride, oxide, nitride and mixed metal oxide, boride or nitride phases. The relative nucleation and growth rates of the boride phases can be influenced by diffusion barriers, e.g. oxide coatings and the relative magnitudes of diffusional fluxes in the separate boride phase. These factors can result in preferential inhibition

Figure 1. Thermodynamic stability of Al_2MgO_4 and Al_2SiO_5 .

Figure 2. Thermodynamic stability of BN , AlN and MgO .

Figure 3 (above). Thermodynamic stability of AlB_2 , AlB_{12} , SiC and Al_4C_3 .

Figure 4 (right). Thermodynamic stability of B_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 .

or growth of the boride phase. In addition, the role of ternary alloy additions, e.g. Mg and Si, can affect the nucleation and growth of the interface and lead to an alteration in the interfacial growth pattern. This can be accomplished by: (i) perturbation of diffusional fluxes in the boride phases, (ii) a change in the intermetallic defect structure or (iii) a change in the phase sequence as a result of the ternary phase additions.

Table I. Free Energy of Formation (ΔG) of Various Compounds in B/Al Composites

	ΔG (J/Mole) $\times 10^{-3}$	
	25°C	527°C
Al ₂ SiO ₅	-4,889.0	-4,393.3
Al ₂ MgO ₄	-4,371.0	-3,951.1
Al ₂ O ₃	-3,160.5	-2,846.3
B ₂ O ₃	-2,389.6	-2,129.0
AlN	- 574.0	- 468.3
BN	- 451.1	- 361.9
AlB ₁₂	- 206.8	- 212.1
MgB ₄	- 103.7	-1,100.0
MgB ₂	- 89.6	- 85.3
AlB ₂	- 65.3	- 61.5

B. B/Al(6061) Interface Reactions

Reaction products at the fiber-matrix interface in the B/Al(6061) system resulting from isothermal exposure at 500°C for various time periods are shown in Figure 5 in a sequence of increasing exposure times. The reaction products exhibit a needle shaped morphology in all specimens examined. Although the particle size of the reaction products (3-4 μ m) remains constant with increasing exposure time, the reaction product density on the fiber surface increases with exposure time until the entire fiber surface is reacted, Figure 5. Further exposure beyond this stage (3.2 $\times 10^4$ s at 500°C) does not alter the appearance of the fiber surface. Micrographs of fiber cross-sections, Figure 6, indicate that reaction at the interface continues and increases the thickness of the reaction zone layer when the composite is exposed beyond the stage at which the entire fiber surface is covered with reaction product.

Composites exposed at 350°C reveal the same morphology of reaction products, but the diffusion-controlled growth is markedly suppressed, Figure 7. Reaction at 350°C for 5 $\times 10^5$ s appears to be less extensive than that at 500°C for 1.6 $\times 10^4$ s, and is comparable to exposure at 500°C for 9 $\times 10^3$ s, Figure 5(b).

C. B/Al(1100) Interface Reactions

The morphology of reaction products and growth kinetics in B/Al(1100) are distinctly different from those in the B/Al(6061) system. Reaction products observed on the boron fiber surface are shown in Figure 8, for a sequence of increasing exposure times. Instead of the needle-shaped particles (Figure 5), the reaction products have a blocky, faceted and often hexagonal shape which becomes more distinct geometrically as exposure time increases. Furthermore,

(a) As-received

(b) Time: 9.0×10^3 s

10 μ m

(c) Time: 1.62×10^4 s

(d) Time: 2.4×10^5 s

Figure 5. Interface reaction products in B/Al (6061) observed on boron fiber surfaces after extracting matrix. Isothermal exposure in argon at 500°C for indicated time periods.

(a) As-received

(b) As-received

(c) Time: 8.6×10^4 s

(d) Time: 8.6×10^4 s

Figure 6. Interface reaction products in B/Al(6061) observed on boron fiber surfaces after extracting matrix. Isothermal exposure in argon at 500°C for indicated time periods.

(a) Time: 2.4×10^5 s (b) Time: 5.0×10^5 s
Figure 7. Interface reaction in B/Al(6061) observed on boron fiber surfaces after extracting matrix. Isothermal exposure in argon at 350°C for indicated time periods.

(a) Time: 9.0×10^3 s

(b) Time: 8.6×10^4 s

(c) Time: 8.6×10^4 s

(d) Time: 2.4×10^5 s

(e) Time: 1.2×10^6 s

Figure 8. Interface reaction products in B/Al(1100) observed on boron fiber surfaces after extracting matrix. Isothermal exposure in argon at 500°C for indicated time periods.

the particle size of the reaction products increases as exposure time increases. For example, exposure at 500°C for 8.6×10^4 s produced fine particles of a size $\sim 1.4 \mu\text{m}$ while exposure for 2.44×10^5 s at the same temperature resulted in a particle size of about $6 \mu\text{m}$. It is also apparent that the interface reaction in the 1100 alloy system is not as extensive as that in the 6061 alloy system as shown previously in Figure 5 and may be attributable to a more coherent Al_2O_3 diffusion barrier.

D. X-Ray Diffraction Analysis of Interface Reaction Products

From a comparison of the measured interplanar spacings with those listed in the ASTM Card File Index, it is concluded that the reaction product in B/Al(6061) is tetragonal AlB_{12} , Table II. Similarly, in B/Al(1100) the reaction product is indentified as hexagonal AlB_2 , Table III. The latter is consistent with the morphology of the reaction product seen in Figure 8.

Table II. Analysis of Diffraction Pattern for Reaction Product in B/Al(6061)

Line	Interplanar Spacing, (\AA)		I/I_1 ASTM 12-640
	Measured	ASTM Card 12-640 ($\alpha\text{-AlB}_{12}$)	
1**	**	4.33 4.13 3.82	70 100 80
2	3.045	3.085	40
3	2.485	2.488	30
4	2.341	2.394	30
5	2.287	2.240	35
6	2.099	2.051	30
7	1.921	1.918	20
8	1.883	1.839	40

** Broad low angle halo from the cellulose acetate tape overlaps the three most intense lines.

Table III. Analysis of Diffraction Pattern for Reaction Product in B/Al(1100)

Line	Interplanar Spacing, (\AA)		I/I_1 ASTM 9-154	Relative* Intensity
	Measured	ASTM Card 9-154 (AlB_2)		
1	**	2.608	40	
2	2.038	2.037	100	VS*
3	1.507	1.505	30	W*

* VS = Very Strong; W = Weak

**Broad low angle halo from the cellulose acetate tape overlaps line #1.

E. Strength and Fracture Morphology

The effect of thermal aging at 500°C in dry argon on room temperature

fracture strength is illustrated in Figure 9. In the 45° fiber orientation, there is an appreciable loss of strength ($\sim 19\%$) after 2.88×10^4 s. However, extended aging up to 2.45×10^5 s causes no further strength decrease. From fracture surface morphology, Figure 10, it is concluded that in the 45° orientation, failure occurs predominantly by matrix shear.

In the 90° fiber orientation, there is a gradual reduction in strength for aging times up to 2.45×10^5 s; the strength decrease is $\sim 25\%$ compared to the as-fabricated level. Representative fracture morphologies in this orientation after aging times of 2.88×10^4 s and 2.45×10^5 s are shown in Figures 11 and 12 respectively. The morphology is characterized by a mixture of fiber splitting, ductile matrix fracture and failure at the fiber-matrix interface. Most of the fiber-matrix interface failures initiate in regions that reflect poor bonding during composite fabrication. The lack of interface reaction during aging is confirmed from the clean boron fiber surfaces exposed at the matching locations on both fracture surfaces - marked A and A' in Figure 11. Further detail showing unreacted fiber is seen in Figure 13. From a sequence of fractographs at increasing aging time it is noted that the fraction of fibers that split in the 90° orientation does increase. This is consistent with the loss in fiber strength reported by White and Wright (4).

A limited number of 0° orientation specimens were tested after comparable aging times to the 45° and 90° orientations. Considerable scatter was evident in the measured fracture strengths. No difference is noted in interfacial product morphology and growth in air vs. argon exposures.

Analysis of Interfacial Reactions

A. Assumptions

Consideration of the interface reactions in composites must include several factors in order to predict reaction zone stability and growth (7,8). These include: binary and ternary phase relationships, structure, diffusion path and the mechanism of intermetallic compound formation as well as the relative diffusional fluxes in the phases. The binary aluminum-boron phase diagram, Figure 14, reveals two stable low temperature phases, AlB_2 and AlB_{12} (9). The ternary aluminum-boron-magnesium system shows two boride, three aluminum-magnesium and four boron-magnesium intermetallics, Figure 15. Details on Al-Mg-B ternary phase stability and solubility are limited.

As a result of limited diffusional and thermodynamic data, the following scenario is postulated for boride phase development in the B/Al(1100) and B/Al(6061) systems. Consideration is given first to the diffusing species in terms of atomic and ionic radii, Table IV. Based on size considerations, it is assumed that $D_B > D_{Si} > D_{Al} > D_{Mg}$.

Table IV. Ionic and Atomic Radii

Atom	Atomic Radius \AA	Valence	Ionic Radius \AA
Al	1.431	+ 3	0.57
B	0.46	+ 3	~ 0.25
Mg	1.594	+ 2	0.78
Si	1.176	+ 4	0.41

Thus, simplistically, it may be considered that boron is the fastest moving species while magnesium would be the slowest. Naturally, the defect structure

Figure 9. Unidirectional tensile strength of B/Al(6061) following exposure in argon at 500°C for the times indicated.

Figure 10. Fracture morphology of 45° orientation unidirectional B/Al(6061) following isothermal exposure in argon at 500°C for 8.6×10^4 s.

Figure 11. Fracture surface morphology of B/Al(6061) following isothermal exposure in argon at 500°C for 2.88×10^4 s.

Figure 12. Fracture surface morphology of B/Al(6061) following isothermal exposure in argon at 500°C for 2.45×10^3 s.

(a)

(b)

Figure 13. Fracture morphology in B/Al(6061) exposed at 500°C for 2.88×10^4 s showing unreacted interface and poor matrix bonding.

Figure 14. The aluminum-boron phase diagram (9).

Figure 15. Intermetallic compounds and stability temperatures for the Al-Mg-B system.

of the intermetallic would greatly influence the diffusion mechanism and the fluxes.

The second consideration is that of thermodynamic stability of the intermetallic compounds. From Table I, AlB_{12} is more stable than AlB_2 and the binary phase diagram, Figure 14, confirms a higher temperature range for AlB_{12} (2070°C) than for AlB_2 (975°C). Based upon these factors, it may be assumed that the AlB_2 phase is less stable and diffusion in the AlB_2 phase is faster than in AlB_{12} at comparable temperatures. Factors which can influence the intermetallic boride diffusion process include defect structure, diffusion mechanism and ternary additions.

B. Interfacial Growth in B/Al(1100)

For the B/Al(1100) interfacial growth, three possible sequences can occur; these are visualized in Figure 16. They include (i) a stable interface reaction with the formation of AlB_2 and AlB_{12} with comparable diffusional fluxes, $J_{AlB_2} \approx J_{AlB_{12}}$, (ii) growth of interfacial products impeded by the oxide barriers Al_2O_3 and B_2O_3 and (iii) the preferential growth of AlB_2 with the disappearance of the AlB_{12} intermetallic based on a larger diffusional flux in the AlB_2 vs. AlB_{12} , i.e. $J_{AlB_2} > J_{AlB_{12}}$. Experimental results and the previous assumptions concerning relative phase stability and the diffusion growth process support the contention that AlB_2 would grow faster than AlB_{12} and could lead to a "missing" AlB_{12} phase.

C. Interfacial Growth in B/Al(6061)

The interfacial reaction product in a 6061 matrix system is modified by the alloy additions of 1.0 wt.% Mg, 0.6 wt.% Si, 0.27 wt.% Cu and 0.20 wt.% Cr. The implications of these additions are significant with regard to (i) the formation of complex oxide, boride and mixed intermetallic phases, Figures 15 and 17. (ii) the alternation of a simple binary, Al-B, diffusion couple into a more complex ternary or quaternary couple and (iii) the alteration of the defect structure and diffusion mechanism of the intermetallic phase based upon polyvalent additions (Mg^{+3} , Si^{+4}). Possible interfacial reaction schemes are shown in Figure 17. These include: (a) interfacial reaction based upon no influence of ternary additions and comparable diffusional fluxes; (b) interfacial reaction based on a ternary Al-Mg-B diffusion path resulting in the formation of two phase regions, e.g. $Al + AlB_2$, $AlB_2 + AlB_{12}$, etc.; (c) interface reaction based upon the growth of the AlB_{12} phase in a ternary diffusion path with $J_{AlB_2} < J_{AlB_{12}}$.

Preliminary Auger electron analysis from extracted as-received and thermally exposed B/Al(6061) composites indicate the presence of magnesium and silicon at the extracted fiber interface. In addition, argon ion profiling reveals that the levels of these alloy additions decreases from a maximum at the fiber surface to a minimum level beyond a depth of $\sim 400\text{\AA}$.

Rationalization of the AlB_{12} growth, as documented in the experimental results, is contingent upon an alteration in the diffusional fluxes in the AlB_2 and AlB_{12} phases based upon ternary additions. For preferential growth of AlB_{12} , $J_{AlB_{12}} > J_{AlB_2}$. Thus, reversal may be accommodated by additions of Mg and Si which can alter the defect structure of the borides, thereby changing the diffusion mechanism and fluxes.

(a) Interface formation where $J_{AlB_2} = J_{AlB_{12}}$

(b) Interface formation with Al₂O₃ and B₂O₃ Oxide Barriers

(c) Preferential growth of AlB₂ when $J_{AlB_2} > J_{AlB_{12}}$

Figure 16. Development of interface reaction zone in B/Al(1100).

(a) Interface formation based upon a binary diffusion couple and $J_{AlB_2} = J_{AlB_{12}}$

(b) Interface formation based upon a ternary diffusion path.

(c) Preferential growth of AlB_{12} when $J_{AlB_{12}} > J_{AlB_2}$.

Figure 17. Development of interface reaction zone in B/Al(6061).

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